

Comparison vegetation indices from different sensors for monitoring grain yield and yield related traits in maize (*Zea mays* L.)

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Single grain yield related traits such as ear length, kernel-row number, as well as the number of kernels per row are important traits for final grain yield of maize. The grain yield and yield related traits are influenced by several factors, either they are environmental or technological. However, methods to assess these traits are laborious and time consuming. Non-destructive and rapid estimation of canopy traits are important for predicting crop growth and managing nitrogen (N) application. Spectral reflectance measurements have provided research opportunities in assessing grain yield and yield related traits, including response to abiotic and biotic stresses. In this view, various sensors have been used to obtain the canopy spectral reflectance for crops grow monitoring in maize. In this study we investigated and compared the performance of two proximal sensors in field trials, an active multispectral optical device named Plant-O-Meter (POM) and GreenSeeker handheld device to assess cultivar differences and parameters affected by different amounts of available nitrogen. In a field experiment, three high-yielding maize cultivars were grown with five different nitrogen (N) supplies of 0, 50, 100, 150 and 200 kg N ha⁻¹. Canopy reflectance of maize cultivars were measured between V5 to V8 growth stages. The results indicated that measuring with the POM sensor within this growth stage can provide early yield estimation and yield related traits, comparable to the GreenSeeker measurements. This publication revealed that Plant-O-Meter device possesses strong potential for accurate plant canopy measurements and can be used to support guide for appropriate application of N fertilization of maize to ensure the maximum yield for specific field condition.

Biography

Dr Nataša Ljubičić senior researcher at BioSense Institute, received Ph.D. degrees from the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia, in 2015 in field of Plant Breeding. She is the author and co-author of more than 30 journal and conference papers on international and national levels. She was involved in several national projects, participates in H2020 and project funded by the EBRD. Her research interests include implementation inovative and smart technology in agricultural investigations, following genotype/environment interaction, phenotypic variability, plant nutrition with the main interest to increase crop yield and crop quality.

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Session name/ number: 13 ([Agronomy and Crop Science](#))

Category: Oral presentation